

A Experiments details in Section 3.

A.1 Datasets

BA-Shapes and Tree-cycles are synthetic node classification datasets. BA-Shapes is composed of 80 house motifs and a base Barabasi-Albert (BA) graph containing 300 nodes. Node labels are divided into four categories, representing vertices, middle, and bottom parts of the houses, or not belonging to any motifs. Tree-cycles consist of a base eight-level binary balanced trees with 80 six-node cyclic motifs. Node labels are binary and denote whether the node belongs to the cycle motif. Mutagenicity and NCI1 are real-world graph classification datasets. Mutagenicity comprises 4337 unique chemical molecules, where nodes represent individual atoms and edges denote different chemical bonds. The labels indicate whether the chemical molecule is mutagenic. NCI1 includes 4110 chemical compounds with labels indicating whether the compound inhibits cancer cell growth. Table 5 provides additional details about these datasets.

A.2 Experimental Hardware

All experiments were conducted on a PC equipped with an NVIDIA RTX 4070 Ti GPU and an Intel Core i5-13600KF processor, supported by 32GB of RAM and 12GB of graphics memory.

A.3 Details about the target GNN

For the target GNN to be explained, we followed the same experimental setup as previous works. Specifically, for node classification, we employed three layers of Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs) with output dimensions set to 20. We concatenated the outputs from these three layers and subsequently subjected them to a linear transformation to derive the node labels. In the case of graph classification, we utilized three layers of GCNs with dimensions of 20 and conducted global max-pooling to generate the graph representations. A subsequent linear transformation layer was employed to derive the graph labels. The target GNN achieved accuracies of 94.1, 97.1, 88.5, and 78.6 on the BA-Shapes, Tree-cycles, Mutagenicity, and NCI1 datasets, respectively.

A.4 Details about the explainer

For the encoder of explainer, we applied a three-layer GCN with output dimensions 32, 32, and 16. The decoder is equipped with a two-layer MLP and an inner product decoder. The discriminator was implemented using a two-layer MLP with a hidden layer dimension of 32. We trained the explainers using a learning rate of 0.003 for 300 epochs in the first stage and 50 epochs in the second stage. All of our experiments and models, including the target GNN, our interpreter, and the baseline models, were implemented using PyTorch and trained with Adam optimizer.

A.5 Downstream Tasks

Node-Level Task For node-level tasks, such as node classification, the interpretation of the target node is designed as the subgraph with the strongest correlation with the prediction result on the computation graph. For a graph with more than thousands of nodes, it is impractical to reconstruct the complete graph for interpreting a single node; Moreover, the auto-encoder can not complete the training based on only one single graph. Therefore, for node-level tasks, we will obtain the subgraph composed of k -hop neighbors of each node

Datasets	BA-Shapes	Tree-cycles	Mutagenicity	NCI1
#Graphs	1	1	4337	4110
#Nodes	700	871	30.32(Avg.)	32.30(Avg.)
#Edges	4110	1950	30.77(Avg.)	29.87(Avg.)
#Labels	4	2	2	2
#Training	300	270	3468	3031
#Validation	50	45	434	411
#Testing	50	45	434	410

Table 6. Details about the datasets.

for training, leading to a compact study on the whole graph (The value of k is set as the number of layers in the target GNN.). When interpreting a specific node, we will use the subgraph consisting of no more than k -hop reconstructed by the encoder for prediction, and these subgraphs are considered as the most relevant and influential part of the input graph to the prediction.

Graph-Level Task For graph-level tasks, such as graph classification, we will let the auto-encoder learn to reconstruct the complete graph structure. When making predictions, a readout function (can be average pooling or maximal pooling) is employed to obtain the graph-level representation from the latent feature Z . Then the discriminator employs the graph representation to make predictions. Experimental results show that this austere readout function is efficient and effective under the constraints of our designed optimizing objective.

A.6 Setting of sparsity hyperparameter γ

Regarding the setting of sparsity, although we recommend setting the sparsity hyperparameter γ to 0.5 to generate an importance score matrix that is relatively balanced, we still suggest adjusting the sparsity differently based on different interpretability requirements to achieve better interpretability (for example, when a concise explanation is needed, lowering the sparsity as much as possible).

A.7 Hyperparameter sensitivity.

To analyze the impact of different hyperparameter settings on the performance of PAGE, we conducted hyperparameter sensitivity experiments on Mutagenicity. We separately varied the values of the hyperparameters λ_1 , λ_2 , and λ_3 while keeping the default parameter settings ($\lambda_1 = 1.0$, $\lambda_2 = 0.1$, $\lambda_3 = 0.01$), and observed the explanation accuracy under different sparsity levels. The experimental results, as shown in 6, indicate that all three hyperparameters have varying influence on the model’s performances. This not only demonstrates the effectiveness of the discriminator module we designed but also underscores the necessity of selecting appropriate values for hyperparameters.

Figure 6. Results about hyperparameter sensitivity.